

ISic3223

Funerary inscription for Kailia Heorte

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 235

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 25.5 cm

Width 24 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 12-28 mm

Text

1. Δαίμοσι
2. χθονίοις
3. Καιλία · Ἔορτή ·
4. ἐβίωσε · ἔτη · ο΄
5. Βλάστη · θυγάτηρ
6. μητρὶ · εὐσεβες
7. τάτη · ἔποισε

Apparatus

Translation (en)

To the underworld spirits. Kailia Heorte lived for 70 years. Blaste, her daughter, made this for a
devoted mother.

Translation (it)

Agli Spiriti sotterranei. Kailia Heorte ha vissuto per 70 anni. Blaste, sua figlia, ha fatto questo
per la madre devota.

Commentary

The phrasing of this text, with the unusual Δάμοσι χθονίοις (one other Sicilian instance, IG XIV.294, from Alcamo), instead of the more normal Θεοῖς Καταχθονίοις (both imitating the Latin Dis Manibus), the uncommon ἐβίωσε instead of ἔζησε ('she lived', Latin vixit), and the unusual form ἔποισε ('she made', usually ἐποίησε, Latin fecit) all suggest the influence of typical Latin formulaic construction (compare nos. 18-21). Both Heorte and Blaste are rare names, mostly found in the eastern Mediterranean in the imperial period, but each is attested once also in Siracusa. Given that Kailia is the Latin Caelia, it is possible that Heorte is intended as a translation of the Latin Festa.

Digital identifiers:

TM 285113

EDCS 15500220

PHI 316209

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 65
Libertini, G 1931. Miscellanea epigrafica. *Archivio Storico per la Sicilia Orientale*. 27: 39-53. At 46 no.11 = Libertini (1981) 96

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